

Localised Heat Transfer Coefficients in Curing Environments: A Heat Flux Approach

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Agenda

1. Introduction and background
2. Proof-of-concept experiment
3. Numerical modelling of the experiment

Introduction

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Curing is a critical stage in thermoset laminate manufacturing

- Mechanical properties of thermoset composite laminates are fully developed during the cure cycle
- Homogenous heating is essential for high-quality composite curing
- Manufacturing processes should be characterised to tailor curing conditions

Effective heat transfer coefficient is used to assess heating in forced convection curing environments

- **Lumped mass calorimetry** is the leading experimental technique to characterise heat transfer coefficients (HTCs) in forced convection curing environments i.e., autoclave, ovens

Plate calorimeter
(Johnston 1997)

$$HTC = \frac{\rho C_p V \frac{dT_s}{dt}}{A(T_\infty - T_s)}$$

Rod calorimeter
(Slesinger et al. 2009)

Effective heat transfer coefficient is used to assess heating in forced convection curing environments

Calorimetry is valuable in characterising:

- Variations in heating across autoclaves and ovens (*Johnston 1997, Hudek 2001, Fisher et al. 2023*)
 - 18 – 200 W/m²K
- Spatial variations in a single curing chamber (*Slesinger et al. 2008, Bohne et al. 2018, Zhu et al. 2021*)
 - Ranges: 60 – 200 W/m²K , 60 – 120 W/m²K , 80 – 130 W/m²K respectively
- Effects of (inter/intra) part shadowing (*Hudek 2001, Weber et al. 2016*)
 - Up to 85% reduction in HTC due to flow obstruction

Many studies implement **HTCs for cure kinetic simulations to optimise cure cycles**

Difficult to characterise complex geometry with calorimetry

Difficult to characterise local variations with calorimetry

A heat flux sensing approach is investigated for characterising localised HTC's

$$HTC = \frac{q_s}{T_\infty - T_s}$$

This approach enables:

- In-situ measurements of parameters
- Finer resolution of spatial variations

Proof-of-concept experiment

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Proof-of-concept experiment: HTC during tool heating

- In a composite curing oven with 8 mm thick aluminium tool plate
- Local sensing across nine (9) locations
- Heating from 20°C to 180°C at 3°C/min. average
- 30-minute dwell at 180°C
- Three (3) experimental runs

$$HTC = \frac{q_s}{T_\infty - T_s}$$

Proof-of-concept experiment: Post-processing of data

A process of sequential steps are required to obtain effective HTC values from the raw experimental data

①

- Sensor voltage converted to heat flux using calibration factor and sensor temperature

②

- Effective HTCs calculated
- Evaluation range determined to remove unphysical values

Localised variations of HTC across the tool were measured

FLOW DIRECTION

Localised variations of HTC across the tool were measured

FLOW DIRECTION

Variations in stream-wise direction:

- HTC highest near air inlets
- Reduces with increasing distance from air inlets
- Up to 19.4% reduction from front to centre
- Negligible reductions from centre to rear

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Variations in transverse direction:

- Lower values in 3, 6, 9 due to obstructions
- Negligible variations

Numerical modelling of the experiment

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Numerical modelling: 3D oven geometry

- Proof-of-concept experiment modelled in OpenFOAM v2312 using Conjugate Heat Transfer (CHT) simulation
- Two-step modelling approach

Numerical modelling: Boundary conditions

To reduce model complexity, 2-step approach was taken

Decrease the solve-time associated with solving the fluid-side equations

Highly unsteady complex flow region between the inlets and the tool – No steady solution

A two-step modelling approach was taken to simulate the conjugate heat transfer:

1. Solve Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier – Stokes (URANS) CFD simulation

- Extract multiple flow snapshots (three snapshots chosen)

2. For each snapshot chosen, solve a transient CHT simulation with a ‘frozen’ flow

URANS equations solved

Decoupled

Only energy equations solved

Time: 0.0 s

URANS flow visualisation at Z-X mid-plane

Time: 0.0 s

Cross-validation: Temperature curves are in close agreement

■ ■ ■ ■ ■ EXP
 ■ ■ ■ ■ ■ SIM

BULK FLOW DIRECTION OVER PLATE

Across heating cycle:

- Average correlation error < 2%
- Max. correlation error < 5%

Sensor position diagram

Temperature time history of EXP and SIM

Cross-validation: Heat flux curve show agreeable trends

■ ■ ■ ■ ■ EXP **—** SIM

BULKFLOW DIRECTION OVER PLATE

- Agreeable trends between EXP and SIM
- Larger errors in heat flux magnitude
- Best correlation in centre column (2, 5, 8)

Avg. heat flux in "peak window". Units in W/m^2

Position	EXP	SIM	Error
HFS 1	735.2	908.9	23.6%
HFS 2	784.7	955.9	21.8%
HFS 3	647.7	954.9	47.4%
HFS 4	699.2	1043.6	49.2%
HFS 5	716.4	916.3	27.8%
HFS 6	672.9	915.4	36.0%
HFS 7	710	875.6	23.3%
HFS 8	663.5	810.3	22.1%
HFS9	662.6	841.2	26.9%

Heat flux time history of EXP and SIM

Larger errors in heat flux profiles due to modelling approach

- Local regions can be impacted heavily depending on the snapshot
- “Frozen” flow assumption preserves transient flow structures that would dissipate

Heat flux time history of EXP and SIM

Larger errors in heat flux profiles due to modelling approach

- Local regions can be impacted heavily depending on the snapshot
- “Frozen” flow assumption preserves transient flow structures that would dissipate
- Location four (4) observes highest local flow velocity hence accumulates largest correlation error

Key summary

- Investigated an alternative experimental approach for characterising HTC's
- Local variations in HTC's captured across a simple tool heating experiment
- Numerical cross-validation shows good correlation in temperature and moderate correlation with heat flux

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Localised heat transfer coefficients during an in-oven composites curing process

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Thank you!
Questions?

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Standard deviations as % of mean value

